

gives a 15 proton multiplet at 2.9 τ (aromatic protons), a two proton singlet at 5.2 τ (-CH₂-protons) and a three proton singlet at 7.7 τ (methyl protons). In the mass spectrum, molecular ion peak at m/e 328 constitutes the base peak.

Reaction of α -methylbenzalidenebenzylamine with diphenylketene: To a boiling xylene solution of the imine (0.01 mole) was added diphenylketene generated by the thermal decomposition⁴ of α -diazo- α -phenylacetophenone⁶. The mixture was heated for a while. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was recrystallized from benzene petroleum ether, m.p. 156°, yield 65%.

Infrared spectrum of the above adduct indicates absorption bands at 1740 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of β -lactum carbonyl. NMR spectrum shows 20 protons as a multiplet at 2.7 τ (aromatic), a two proton singlet at 5.2 τ (methylene) and a three proton singlet at 7.6 τ (methyl).

In case of hydroxy substituted imine, esterification of phenolic group also took place. Thus the cycloadduct having esterified phenolic group was obtained.

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Interaction of 2-Amino-4-Phenyl-5-Arylazothiazoles with 2-Nitro, 3-Nitro and 4-Nitro Benzaldehydes

RAJEEV JAIN*, SUDHA TYAGI and SHARAD AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee,
Roorkee-247 672

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ALTHOUGH various N-aryl-N'-2-thiazolythioureas have been prepared by the interaction of arylisothiocyanates and 2-aminothiazole derivatives, the reaction of benzaldehydes with thiazole derivatives has not been investigated. Moreover, thiazole derivatives are of considerable interest from therapeutic point of view because of their utility as antifungal¹, antibacterial², antitumor³, anthelmintic⁴, local anaesthetic, diuretic⁵ and adrenergic agents. Thiazole derivatives contain thiourea moiety and,

therefore, like urea derivatives can possibly act as hypoglycemic agents⁶. In view of these possibilities, various substituted thiazole derivatives (A) were synthesised to study their biological activities.

The compounds (A) described in this communication have been synthesised by reacting 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles⁷ with different nitro derivatives of benzaldehydes. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis and ir and mass spectral studies. The reactivity of 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazole was smooth and the product was obtained in good yield. Colour of all these compounds ranges from dark yellow to brown.

Experimental

Preparation of 4-phenyl-5-arylozo-2-(azomethine-4-nitrophenyl) thiazole: 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazole (0.002 mol) was dissolved in alcohol (25 ml) and a hot solution of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.002 mol) in alcohol (20 ml) was added to it. The contents were refluxed for 3 hrs in presence of 0.2 ml piperidine. On cooling, shining crystals separated out which were recrystallised from 60% ethyl alcohol. All m.p.s are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in KBr film on a Backmann IR spectrophotometer and mass spectral studies were carried out on a Varian Mat-CH-7 mass spectrophotometer. 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles were prepared by the reported method⁷.

Analysis: m.p. 165°; Found: N, 16.7%. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₅N₃O₂S; N, 16.94%; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1610 cm⁻¹ (-N=N-), 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=C or C=N) 830-690 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{CH}_2\text{OH}}$ at 420 nm for -N=N- grouping and 270 nm for C₆H₅NO₂; M⁺ at m/e 413.

Other 4-phenyl-5-arylozo-2-(azomethine-3-nitrophenyl)/4-phenyl-5-arylozo-2-(azomethine-2-nitrophenyl) thiazoles were prepared in the same way by taking suitably substituted nitrobenzaldehydes. Their characteristics are compiled in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 4-PHENYL-5-ARYLAZO-2-(AZOMETHINE-NITROPHENYL) THIAZOLES

Sl. No.		R	m.p. °C	Yield %
1.	R=4-NO ₂	H	165	50
2.	"	2-OH ₃	160	60
3.	"	3-OH ₃	180	60
4.	"	4-OH ₃	116	65
5.	"	2-OCH ₃	148	50
6.	"	3-OCH ₃	142	50